

20.11.2025

SOILS/STR/24/2025

Ravikumar
Director
Urav Advanced Learning Systems Pvt. Ltd

Sir,

Sub: Sample analysis results – reg.

The submitted samples have been analyzed and the results are given below

Sample name	Alkalinity	Calcium
	(mg/l)	
B	334.4	32.06
C	466.4	86.57
D	404.8	80.16

Yours faithfully

SANDEEP S.
Principal Scientist and Head,
Dept. of Soil Science,
KSCSTE - KFRI, Peechi